

The C-4 carbonyls in all the compounds appeared in the region of 175 ppm. The chemical shifts of C-2 and C-3 carbons of the compounds III, VI, IX and X occurred in the region of 155 and 114 ppm respectively, whereas downfield shifts were observed for C-2 and C-3 in I and XI due to the presence of -CHO group at C-3. C-8 carbons in all the compounds resonated at the same regions irrespective of the *meta* substituents in the phenyl ring. C-4a carbons in the compounds III, VI, IX and X appeared in the region of 124 ppm whereas it absorbed at about 120 ppm for the compounds I and XI. C-5 and C-7 resonated uniformly in all the compounds except for the compounds VI and X where downfield shifts of about 1.5 ppm and about 3 ppm respectively were observed due to *ortho* effect². The chemical shifts of C-6 in all the compounds were in conformity with their structures: compounds I, III and XI absorbed in the same region but downfield shift of ~10 ppm and ~6 ppm and an upfield shift of ~5.5 ppm were observed for the compounds VI, IX and X respectively for the substituent effects of CH₃, Cl and Br groups at C-6. Chemical shifts of C-8a in all the compounds appeared nearly at the same position. The chemical shifts for C-2', C-4' and C-5' and those of phenyl ring carbons were uniform and in conformity with their structures.

The one bond coupling constants (J_{C-H}) of the oxygenated carbon C-2 in III, VI, IX and X was about 200 Hz which was closely comparable to the J_{C-H} for C-2 in I, indicating that C-2 was not fully substituted. J_{C-H} for aromatic and methyl carbons were in the normal range.

TABLE I—CARBON-13 CHEMICAL SHIFTS AND COUPLING CONSTANTS (J_{C-H}) OF I, III, VI, IX, X AND XI

	I	III	VI	IX	X	XI*
C-2	160.4 (198.1)	154.6 (200.1)	155.0 (199.6)	154.6 (201.0)	154.6 (201.1)	165.6
C-3	125.0	113.7	113.0	114.1	114.2	122.3
C-4	175.6	175.8	175.8	174.8	174.6	175.3
C-4a	120.1	123.5	123.1	124.5	124.8	120.0
C-5	126.3 (164.0)	125.5 (166.5)	124.8 (164.0)	125.0 (161.6)	128.4 (161.1)	125.4
C-6	125.8 (160.5)	125.4 (166.7)	135.7	131.6	119.1	125.3
C-7	134.6 (164.0)	133.7 (164.2)	135.2 (164.0)	134.0 (169.0)	136.8 (168.2)	134.2
C-8	118.4 (167.4)	118.1 (166.1)	117.9 (165.1)	119.9 (168.1)	120.1 (168.3)	116.9
C-8a	155.9	155.7	154.0	154.0	154.5	
C-2'		139.5	139.7	139.1	139.1	
C-4', 5'		132.6	131.4	131.6	132.0	
C-1'', 1'''		127.5	127.5	127.5	127.5	
C-2'', 2''', 6'', 6'''		127.5 (162.2)	127.5 (162.0)	127.5 (159.3)	127.5 (159.7)	
C-3'', 3''', 5'', 5'''		128.3 (160.2)	128.3 (160.4)	128.4 (160.5)	128.4 (161.1)	
C-4'', 4'''		127.1 (160.7)	127.3 (159.4)	127.2 (160.5)	127.2 (160.7)	
CHO	188.2 (186.5)					188.1
CH ₃			20.7 (125.2)			

* In d₆-DMSO; C-8a signal merged with noise.

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Search for Potent Anthelmintics-Part XIV. Benzoxazolylthio/Oxyethylureas and Thioureas

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A number of N¹-(2-benzoxazolylthio/oxyethyl)-N³-alkyl/arylureas and thioureas were synthesised as possible anthelmintics.

Several thioureas^{1,2} including benzimidazolyl thioureas³ have very recently been found as effective anthelmintics. A few ureas^{4,5} have also been known to reduce hook worms in dogs and possess nematocidal effect against *Panegrellus redivivus*. Moreover, some benzoxazole derivatives^{6,7} exhibited anthelmintic properties in mice and chickens. In view of these findings, it was considered desirable to synthesise the title ureas and thioureas with a view to determining their anthelmintic efficacy.

Benzoxazol-2-thione/one^{8,9} was refluxed with β -chloroethanolamine hydrochloride¹⁰ in the presence of acetone and anhydrous K₂CO₃ to afford 2-(2-aminoethylthio/oxy) benzoxazole. The latter was treated with various alkyl/aryl isocyanates or isothiocyanates to furnish the desired ureas and thioureas.

The results of anthelmintic screening of these compounds will be communicated later on.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

I. 2-(2-Aminoethylthio)benzoxazole and 2-(2-aminoethoxy) benzoxazole :

A mixture of benzoxazol-2-thione or benzoxazol-2-one (.01 mole), β -chloroethanolamine hydrochloride (.01 mole), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (.02 mole) and acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 16 to 20 hr on a steam bath. It was then cooled and filtered. Acetone was distilled off from the filtrate and the crude product obtained was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	X	X'	n	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%Nitrogen	
								Found	Calcd.
1. ^a	S	O	2	C ₆ H ₅	232	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.04	13.42
2. ^b	S	O	2	CH ₃	145	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	16.16	16.73
3.	S	S	2	C ₆ H ₅	135	52	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.22	12.76
4. ^c	S	S	2	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	120	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ OIN ₂ OS ₂	11.11	11.55
5.	S	S	2	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	85	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ OS ₂	10.72	10.29
6.	S	S	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	170	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	12.54	12.24
7.	S	S	2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	128	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	11.81	12.24
8.	S	S	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	145	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	12.52	12.24
9.	S	S	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	154	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	11.98	11.69
10.	S	S	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	122	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	11.27	11.69
11.	S	S	2	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	125	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ OS ₂	11.46	11.08
12.	S	S	2	C ₆ H ₁₁	130	65	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ OS ₂	12.16	12.54
13.	O	O	2	C ₆ H ₅	80	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	14.50	14.14
14.	O	S	2	C ₆ H ₅	68	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.10	13.42
15. ^d	O	S	2	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	78	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	11.20	10.71
16.	O	S	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.52	12.84
17. ^e	O	S	2	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	110	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.43	12.84
18.	O	S	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	86	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.29	12.84
19.	O	S	2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ O ₂ C ₆ H ₄	84	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.70	12.24
20.	O	S	2	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	92	56	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.61	12.24
21. ^f	O	S	2	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	90	62	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	11.98	11.57
22.	O	S	2	C ₆ H ₁₁	106	66	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.54	13.17

I.R. Spectral Bands in cm⁻¹

	amide C=O	-SCH ₂ -	NH-Str.	-C-N S	-O-CH ₂ -
a	1650	1430	3300	—	—
b	1650	1415	3300	—	—
c	—	1418	3170	1090	—
d	—	—	3160	1150	1220
e	—	—	3100	1145	1250
f	—	—	3100	1050	1250

Analysis and m.p.'s of the above two compounds thus prepared are given as follows :

- i. 2-(2-Aminoethylthio)benzoxazole, m.p. 160° (Found : N, 14.12 ; C₉H₁₀N₂OS requires N, 14.43%)
- ii. 2-(2-Aminoethoxy)benzoxazole, m.p. 120° (Found : N, 15.36 ; C₉H₁₀N₂O₂ requires N, 15.73%)

II. N¹-(2-benzoxazolylthio/oxyethyl)-N³-alkyl/arylureas and thioureas :

2-(2-Aminoethylthio/oxy)benzoxazole (0.01 mole) and alkyl/aryl isothiocyanate or isocyanate (0.01 mole) were refluxed in anhydrous benzene (30 ml) for 4 to 6 hrs. A solid separated on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol or benzene-petroleum ether (Table 1).

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Chemical Examination of *Lindenbergia indica*

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LINDENBERGIA *indica* (N. O. Scrophulariaceae) is an annual erect herb found throughout India. The juice of the plant is given in chronic bronchitis and mixed with that of coriander applied to skin eruptions^{1,2}. No work has been reported in literature on this plant. A systematic chemical examination of *L. indica* was, therefore, undertaken and the results are reported in the present communication.

The air-dried powdered plant (2 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) in a Soxhlet extractor. The extract was concentrated to a small volume (200 ml) and kept in a refrigerator overnight whereby a yellow mass deposited. The deposit was filtered, washed with petroleum ether, taken in benzene and chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether (40-60°) removed the waxy material. Further elution with petroleum ether : benzene mixture (7 : 3 v/v) gave a crystalline solid (800 mg) which when recrystallised from benzene afforded needles, m.p. 281°, C₃₀H₅₀O. It was characterised as friedelan-3-β-ol by spectral data^{3,4} and by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 291° and benzoate, m.p. 198-9°.

The defatted plant material was then extracted exhaustively with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the thick viscous mass so obtained was extracted with petroleum ether to remove any waxy material and chlorophyll. The residual mass was extracted with benzene and acetone successively. Benzene extract was concentrated and chromatographed over alumina. Elution with benzene and chloroform (7 : 3 v/v) mixture yielded a compound (670 mg)

which when recrystallised from methanol-chloroform mixture afforded needles, m.p. 310°, C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺, m/e 456) and characterised as oleanolic acid by comparison of its spectral data^{3,4} and properties of its acetate methyl ester derivative and oxidised product⁵.

The acetone extract was concentrated, dried and extracted with absolute ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to a syrup. Addition of excess of chloroform to the ethanolic syrup, precipitated a resinous mass. The resinous mass was separated by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated, dissolved in water and kept in a refrigerator for a week, whereby free flavone settled down at the bottom. It was separated and dissolved in a little of dried acetone, adsorbed over magnesol column and eluted with ethyl acetate saturated with water whereby a yellow compound was obtained. The compound on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 24° and identified as 7-hydroxy flavone by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data^{6,7} and preparation of its derivatives. The filtrate obtained after separation of free flavone was extracted with ethylacetate for several times. The extract was concentrated and chromatographed over magnesol using ethyl acetate saturated with water as eluate, whereupon a yellow compound was obtained. The compound on crystallisation from methanol : ethanyl acetate mixture (1 : 1 v/v), melted at 185-7° and characterised as quercitrin by m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectrum with authentic sample.

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